

ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS OF THIRD-YEAR ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS OF COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION, BATANGAS STATE UNIVERSITY PABLO BORBON CAMPUS

REYDEL A. PANOPIO¹, JORELL YCES DAVID², DESSA ROSE PUNZALAN³,
JUAN MIGUEL CADEVIDA⁴

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0939-3344>

reydel.panopio@g.batstate-u.edu.ph

Batangas State University - Pablo Borbon Campus

Rizal Ave, Extension, Batangas, Philippines

ABSTRACT

Writing literacy is one of the most important skills that students must learn in the academe. Specifically, students taking a degree in education, particularly the English major students, should be good enough to write an academic composition. Thus, this endeavor sought to assess the academic writing skills of the third-year English major students of College of Teacher Education, Batangas State University - Pablo Borbon Campus. The researchers assessed the writing skills of the respondents in terms of citing evidence, boosting claims, interpreting available literature, addressing counterclaims, and the use of hedging. Also, they determined the challenges encountered by the respondents in academic writing and prepared a set of writing activities that will improve the academic writing skills of the students. The study used a descriptive qualitative research design where the respondents, the third-year BSEd English major students were asked to write two compositions; the first is a pre-essay without defined instructions while the other one is a guided and well-instructed essay. A self-structured scoring rubric which uses the four-scoring scale such as exemplary, accomplished, developing, and beginning were used to score the output of the students. After that, the respondents ranked the prepared checklist regarding the difficulties they experienced while writing their essays. The results revealed that the third-year English major students' academic writing skills in terms of citing evidence and hedging are still in the developing stage. While in terms of boosting claims, interpreting available literature, and addressing counterclaims, it was found out that they are at accomplished level. On the other hand, the findings showed that the respondents experienced difficulties organizing their thoughts to begin their essays. They also encountered problems in coming up with a clear topic sentence and supplying their writings with facts and supporting information. As conclusion, the researchers prepared a set of writing activities in a form of book entitled "Let's Practice: Towards Good Academic Writing" that will enhance the academic writing skills of the respondents.

Keywords: English language teaching; academic writing skills; qualitative study; scoring rubrics and weighted mean; Philippines